

Synthesis of Multicomponent Oxide Nanohybrids for Environmental Remediation

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Abstract—Phenol is a hazardous material found in many industrial wastewaters. Photocatalytic degradation and furthermore catalyst doping are promising techniques in purpose of effective phenol removal, which have been studied comprehensively in this decade. In this study, Fe, Cr codoped TiO₂ were prepared by sol-gel method, and its photocatalytic activity was investigated through degradation of phenol under visible light. The catalyst was characterized by XRD, SEM, FT-IR, BET, and EDX. The results showed that nanoparticles possess anatase phase, and the average size of nanoparticles was about 21 nm. Also, photocatalyst has significant surface area. Effect of experimental parameters such as pH, irradiation time, pollutant concentration, and catalyst concentration were investigated by using Design-Expert® software. 98% of phenol degradation was achieved after 6h of irradiation.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, photocatalysts have been extensively investigated. Photocatalysts are utilized in many applications such as hydrogen production, solar cells, and wastewater treatment. TiO₂ gained the main focus because of its properties: non-toxicity, low cost, and chemical stability. However, large band gap of TiO₂ (3.0-3.2 eV) causes TiO₂ to show photocatalytic activity under ultraviolet (UV) irradiation. A wide range of effort has been made to extend the spectral response of TiO₂ to visible light by metal or non-metal doping. Doping can be achieved by various methods like sol-gel method, hydrothermal method, and wet-impregnation method. Akpan and Hameed stated the advancement in sol-gel method [1]. Sol-gel, modified sol-gel, and other kinds of sol-gel processes were investigated along with single, nonmetal, metal and codoping of titanium dioxide. In most cases of codoping, especially when one element is metal, photocatalytic activity is improved [2]. Kerkez-Kuyumcu et al. investigated a comparative study of the doping of six successive transition metal elements for removal of dyes under visible light [3]. Photocatalyst was prepared by modified precipitation method. Cu/TiO₂ showed highest photocatalytic activity under visible light among the other transition metals. Liu et al. reported synthesis of Fe, N, codoped TiO₂ through hydrothermal method [4]. Photocatalytic activity was examined through degradation of methylene blue solution under visible light. In the present study, sol-gel method was used to synthesize Fe, Cr codoped TiO₂. Then, it was subjected to several characterization methods.

II. PHOTOCATALYST SYNTHESIS

A. Experimental

Titanium isopropoxide (TTIP), nitric acid, ethanol, Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, and Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O were procured from Merck® and were used without further purification. Initially, 5 ml of TTIP was mixed with 50 ml ethanol under magnetic stirring at room temperature. Then, appropriate amount of metal precursor was added to the solution while vigorous stirring. Finally, greenish gel was resulted shortly after 5 ml of nitric acid was added. The resulting gel was dried in room temperature for three days then was calcinated at 400 °C for 4 h to give TiO₂ powder. Single and codoping TiO₂ nanoparticles were synthesized using almost the same method. The appropriate amount of Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O or/and Cr(NO₃)₃·6H₂O was calculated from desired molar ratio of Fe/Ti=0.01 and Cr/Ti=0.005 and then dissolved in anhydrous ethanol, which was added to the distilled water prior to the hydrolysis of TTIP.

Fig. 1 XRD pattern of Fe/Cr codoped TiO₂ : (a) XRD patterns of materials: (A) Cr-doped TiO₂ (B) Fe-doped TiO₂ (C) Fe and Cr codoped TiO₂ (D) TiO₂ calcinated at 400 °C. O: Anatase phase [5] (b) Current study XRD pattern of Fe/Cr codoped TiO₂

B. Characterization

The phase compositions of samples were determined by a D8 ADVANCE X-ray diffractometer (XRD) equipped with graphite monochromatized Cu K α radiation. The morphology of the sample was observed by using scanning electron microscopy (VEGA3 SB – EasyProbe) along with EDX. FTIR analysis was operated by PerkinElmer FT-IR with the model of Spectrum RXI. BET surface area, total pore volume, and the pore size volume of the catalysts were measured by N₂ physisorption at 77.26 K using Micromeritics ASAP 2020 V3.03 system.

XRD patterns of codoped TiO₂ are shown in Fig. 1. The distinct peaks of anatase phase of TiO₂ is demonstrated in Fig. 1 (a) and compared to current study XRD pattern (shown in Fig. 1 (b)) confirms formation of anatase TiO₂.

FT-IR spectrum of codoped TiO₂ is given Fig. 2. A broadband can be seen in the 400-900 cm⁻¹ region which is attributed to Ti-O-Ti bond of anatase titania [4]. Peaks at 3400 and 1600 cm⁻¹ represents the O-H vibrational bond and water absorption respectively [6].

Fig. 3 shows the SEM results of mentioned catalyst. It can be figured from the photo that particle size varies between 1629 nm, and the estimated average size is 21 nm. Elemental compositions of codoped TiO₂ can be determined from EDX diagram which are shown in Table I. Results show that they are in good agreement with theoretical calculations.

TABLE II
RESULTS OF BET ANALYSIS

Photocatalyst	Total surface area (m ² /g)	Total pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Average pore diameter (Å)
Fe, Cr codoped TiO ₂		0.185	73.42

III. DETERMINATION OF PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION

Photocatalytic activity was evaluated by degradation of phenol in aqueous solutions with dispersed codoped TiO₂ powders. The photoreaction was conducted in a 150-mL cylindrical vessel above a magnetic stirrer. A 35-W Xenon lamp was located above the vessel. Before irradiation, the suspension was stirred for 30 min in the dark to obtain equilibrium. Permanent air bubbling (rate of 3.5 lit/min) was applied during irradiation in order to keep the concentration of the dissolved oxygen constant. Aliquots of suspension were withdrawn at specified times then centrifuged at 5300 rpm for 30 min. The residual concentration of phenol was analyzed with a Fluorescence Spectrophotometer.

In this study, Design-Expert® software (Ver. 10) was utilized to design the experiments. The ranges and levels of independent variables are shown in Table III. The detailed the

As it is shown in Fig. 4 (b), phenol degradation rate increased with time. 98% removal is achieved in 6 h. Also, the highest designed experiments along with experimental and predicted values of the response are given in Table IV.

TABLE III
THE LEVELS AND RANGES OF VARIABLES IN CCD EXPERIMENT DESIGN

Name	Units	-1 level	+1 level	-alpha	+alpha
A pH		2.25	9	3	1.3
B Time	h	0.4	4.75	1	
C Catalyst concentration	g/lit		1	0.1	
D Phenol concentration	ppm		70	10	

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Effect of pH

According to results of ANOVA, pH is the second most important parameter in phenol degradation as shown in Fig. 4 (a). It indicates that with increasing of pH, the rate of phenol degradation also increases. Degradation of phenol has been found to be insignificant at low pH values. This phenomenon is due to high concentration of hydroxide in alkaline solutions, which means there is more OH⁻ to react with phenyl ring [8].

B. Effect to Time

degradation rate took place in the first 4 h of reaction. After that, rate decreased to become constant after 6 h [9].

C. Effect of Catalyst Concentration

Fig. 4 (c) demonstrates a maximum peak. In the other words, in the ascending section, increasing the amount of catalyst leads to the increase in the surfaces on which phenol can be adsorbed. Meanwhile, in the descending part, when the amount of the catalyst increases, phenol degradation rate decreases. This phenomenon can be attributed from screening effect [10]. After a certain amount, the solution will become opaque, so the contaminant will receive less intensity of light.

TABLE IV
CCD EXPERIMENTS ALONG WITH ACTUAL VALUES OF RESPONSE

No. of experiment	Time (hr)	Catalyst concentration (g/lit)	Phenol concentration (ppm)	Phenol Degradation under visible light (%)
	3.50	0.70		33.17
	2.25	0.40		24.34
	4.75	0.40		49.73
	6.00	0.70		56.59
	4.75	1.00		34.67
	3.50	0.70		33.42
	2.25	0.40		17.98
	2.25	0.40		13.85

4.75	0.40	69.89
4.75	1.00	51.66
3.50	1.30	26.41
3.50	0.70	33.86
3.50	0.70	13.02
2.25	1.00	22.79
4.75	0.40	41.23
2.25	1.00	24.40
3.50	0.70	69.05
3.50	0.10	11.83
4.75	0.40	34.66
3.50	0.70	34.27
3.50	0.70	34.70
3.50	0.70	35.86
2.25	1.00	32.33
2.25	1.00	15.15
2.25	0.40	34.19
3.50	0.70	35.09
3.50	0.70	62.73
4.75	1.00	38.80
1.00	0.70	11.72

4.75	1.00	52.83
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D. Effect of Initial Phenol Composition

Fig. 4 (d) indicates that phenol degradation vs initial phenol composition has a descending trend. With increasing organic contaminant but keeping the catalyst constant, it hinders them to adsorb on TiO₂ surface resulting in lower degradation rate [11].

E. Modeling Removal Rate of Phenol

Design-Expert® based on the results of experiments, shown in Table IV, models the removal rate of phenol. Hence, for modeling, Response Surface method was used, and Central Composite design was chosen. The equation, to show relations between dependent parameter (percent removal of phenol) and other parameters, which was obtained using quadratic model, is shown in (1):

$$34.72 + 9.15A + 11.59B + 0.66C + 3.69D + 1.83A^2 + 1.59B^2 + 3.7C^2 + 3.99D^2$$

where A, B, C, and D are the coded values of experimental parameters pH, irradiation time (h), catalyst concentration or

C₀ (gr/lit), and phenol composition (ppm). R-squared of results. 0.9165 indicates that the model is in good compatibility of the

Fig. 4 Percent removal of phenol in respect of parameters. (a) Percent removal of phenol with respect to pH at constant condition of time=3.5h, $C_0=0.7$ gr/lit and phenol concentration=50 ppm. (b) Percent removal of phenol with respect to time at constant condition of pH=7, $C_0=0.7$ gr/lit, and phenol concentration=50 ppm (c) Percent removal of phenol with respect to C_0 at constant condition of pH=7, time=3.5h, and phenol concentration=50 ppm (d) Percent removal of phenol with respect to phenol concentration at constant condition of pH=7, time=3.5h, and $C_0=0.7$ g/lit

TABLE V
OPTIMAL CONDITION

Effective parameters	Optimal value
pH	
Irradiation time (h)	
Catalyst concentration (gr/lit)	
Phenol concentration (ppm)	

TABLE VI
COMPARATIVE RESULTS OF PHENOL REMOVAL STUDIES

Type of process	Irradiation time (h)	Phenol concentration (ppm)	Phenol degradation (%)	Researchers
N TiO ₂ + Xe				[12]
CuO/ZnO/TiO ₂ + UV				[13]
Fe TiO ₂ + solar light		1.88		[14]
Cu TiO ₂		158.75		[15]
Fe/Cr TiO ₂ + Xe			98%	This study

F. Optimal Condition

Design-Expert[®] can estimate the optimal condition based on the given results, which is shown in Table V. 98% of phenol removal can be achieved in this condition.

Table VI shows comparative results of works of researchers with this study. Results show that this method is more efficient in time and catalyst consumption, besides the enhancement of the phenol degradation.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, phenol degradation from wastewater using Fe/Cr codoped TiO₂ was investigated. It can be concluded from the experiments that codoping of titania increases photocatalytic activity meaning that iron and chromium are good dopants due to

their similar radius to titanium [16]. Furthermore, alkaline environment, suitable concentration of catalyst, and longer irradiation time can help to increase the removal rate. In optimal condition, phenol can be removed completely.

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